

Forging active partnerships: The role of academic libraries in DH education

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As more and more humanities scholars try to harness the innovative affordances that can emanate from the use of digital technologies, it becomes increasingly important for academic libraries to develop appropriate forms of support for digital humanities research.¹ While librarians have already been organising workshops and other types of classes topics such as open access, data management and digital preservation during the past few years, many academic libraries are currently in the process of exploring new services and training opportunities in the field of data science. In 2019, the UKB working group on Digital Humanities made an inventory of the various courses that are offered already at Dutch universities, and has collected a number of best practices that arose from these initial experiences.

One important finding is that many academic libraries in the Netherlands actually aspire to develop into centres of expertise in the field of data science. They increasingly recruit employees with a background in computer science or in the digital humanities, and they additionally stimulate their existing staff to follow courses on programming and on statistics.² At Maastricht University, for instance, a series of workshops have been organised to enhance the digital proficiency of its librarians, and in 2017, the KB, the VU Amsterdam and Leiden University have collaborated during the organisation of the DH clinics, which was essentially an educational programme which sought to familiarise Dutch academic librarians with the tools and concepts that are central to DH research.³ Many librarians have also had the opportunity to improve their understanding of the technologies that underpin digital humanities research via an active involvement in actual research projects. At Leiden University, digital scholarship librarians have made important contributions to a research project which aims to analyse a large corpus of digitized egodocuments using computational methods.

Capitalising on their newly developed knowledge, a number of academic libraries have also designed workshops and courses which specifically targeted academic staff. Such courses were generally organised for the benefit of researchers who suspected that computational and algorithmic methods could enrich their research, but who lacked the skills and the knowledge that is needed to get started at a practical level. At Utrecht University, the library organises regular courses on data analysis in R, and Leiden University Libraries also organises workshops on programming in Python. The Python courses offered in Leiden proved to be in high

¹ Good overviews of new services and collaborative models are offered in Kear, Robin, *Digital Humanities, Libraries, and Partnerships: A Critical Examination of Labor, Networks, and Community* (San Diego: Elsevier Science, 2018) and Martin, Alison MacKenzie and Lindsey, ed., *Developing Digital Scholarship: Emerging Practices in Academic Libraries* (London: Facet Publishers, 2016)

² Similar developments can be observed in the United States and in other European Countries, see, amongst others, Green, Harriett E., “Facilitating Communities of Practice in Digital Humanities: Librarian Collaborations for Research and Training in Text Encoding”, *The Library Quarterly*, 84 (2014) <<https://doi.org/10.1086/675332>>, or McRostie, Donna, and Leo Konstantelos, “Supporting Digital Scholarship and the Digital Humanities: A Collaboration on Concept, Space, and Services Between the Library and the Faculty of Arts at the University of Melbourne”, in *Collaboration and the Academic Library: Internal and External, Local and Regional, National and International*, 2018 <<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102084-5.00011-0>>

³ Michiel Cock, Lotte Wilms and Ben Companjen, “DH Clinics: Dutch librarians' tour of DH”, <<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3271116>> ; See also <<https://dhclinics.github.io/DH>>

demand among humanities scholars. They offer a basic and accessible introduction to programming in Python, aimed specifically at researchers and teachers without prior coding skills. In addition to these dedicated courses, many librarians have experimented with the development of smaller teaching modules which could be incorporated flexibly into existing curricula, thereby reducing the workload of university lecturers.⁴

This paper explores the role of academic libraries in the field of DH education. Additionally, it aims to raise awareness of the expertise that may exist within libraries, and to encourage university lecturers to consider stimulating and fruitful collaborations with academic librarians.

⁴ Sheila Corral and Liz Jolly, "Innovations in Learning and Teaching in Academic Libraries: Alignment, Collaboration, and the Social Turn", in *New Review of Academic Librarianship*, 25 (2019), 2-4, <<https://doi.org/10.1080/13614533.2019.1697099>>